

Supplementary Materials for

**Alterations in the chondrocyte surfaceome
in response to pro-inflammatory cytokines**

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This PDF file (Additional File #7) includes:

Figures S3–S12. Uncropped western blot membrane images

Figure S3. Uncropped western blot membrane image for the cropped bands shown in **Figure 2A**.

Figure S4. Uncropped western blot membrane image for the cropped bands shown in **Figure 2B**.

Figure S5. Uncropped western blot membrane image for the cropped bands shown in **Figure 2C**.

Figure S6. Uncropped western blot membrane image for the cropped bands shown in **Figure 2D**.

Figure S7. Uncropped western blot membrane image for the cropped bands shown in **Figure 5A**.

Figure S8. Uncropped western blot membrane image for the cropped bands shown in **Figure 5B**.

Figure S9. Uncropped western blot membrane image for the cropped bands shown in **Figure 5C** and **6A**.

Figure S10. Uncropped western blot membrane image for the cropped bands shown in **Figure 5D** and **6B**.

Figure S11. Uncropped western blot membrane image for the cropped bands shown in **Figure 5E**.

Figure S12. Uncropped western blot membrane image for the cropped bands shown in **Figure 5F**.